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HELICOBACTER PYLORI AS A KEY FACTOR IN THE PROGRESSION OF CHRONIC GASTRITIS TO GASTRIC CANCER (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Abstract:

Infection caused by *Helicobacter pylori* remains one of the most common human bacterial infections and a key etiological factor in chronic gastritis and gastric cancer. Colonization of the gastric mucosa by *H. pylori* initiates a cascade of inflammatory and immune reactions, which in the absence of eradication can progress from chronic gastritis to atrophy and gastric adenocarcinoma. Pathogenetic mechanisms include the action of virulence factors of the bacteria (in particular CagA, VacA, BabA, OipA), activation of pro-inflammatory signaling pathways (NF- κ B, MAPK), induction of IL-8 and other cytokines, formation of reactive oxygen species and reactive nitrogen species, as well as impaired cell proliferation and apoptosis. CagA-positive strains are associated with more pronounced inflammation, faster development of atrophy and a higher risk of adenocarcinoma. Chronic persistent inflammation also leads to DNA damage, which in turn is a trigger for carcinogenesis.

Keywords: gastric adenocarcinoma, *H. pylori* infection, , chronic gastritis

Materials and methods: we conducted a literature review based on articles published in PubMed databases over the past 10 years. Current information on the role of *H. pylori* infection in the development of chronic gastritis and stomach cancer was analyzed.

The goal was to analyze scientific works, literary sources and determine the role of *H. pylori* infection in the occurrence of chronic gastritis and stomach cancer.

Relevance: It has been known for over a century that bacteria are normally present in the human stomach. However, it was previously believed that these bacteria are not true colonizers of the stomach. About 50 years ago, Barry Marshall and Robin Warren described the successful isolation and cultivation of a helical species of bacteria later known as *Helicobacter pylori* [1]. *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) infection is the main pathogenic factor in the development of peptic ulcer disease of the gastroduodenal zone and gastric cancer, as well as other types of gastric and extragastric diseases [2,3]. The only natural reservoir of *H. pylori* is the human stomach. *H. pylori* infection usually occurs in childhood and persists throughout the host's life in the absence of antimicrobial treatment. The bacterium can be transmitted from person to person by oral-oral or fecal-oral routes [4].

Studies have shown that *H. pylori* colonization of the stomach can lead to a variety of upper gastrointestinal diseases, such as chronic gastritis,

peptic ulcer disease, gastric mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue (MALT) lymphoma, and gastric adenocarcinoma [1]. Epidemiological studies show that 2–3% of people infected with *H. pylori* develop gastric adenocarcinoma, and 0.1% develop MALT. According to statistical estimates, up to 45% of the world's population is chronically colonized with *H. pylori* and approximately 15% of infected people develop gastric ulcers. However, even when the infection is asymptomatic, *H. pylori* infection can lead to peptic ulcer disease and gastric cancer [4]. In recent years, there has been a significant decrease in the prevalence of *H. pylori*. From 2015 to 2022, the prevalence of *H. pylori* infection among adults worldwide decreased from 50 to 44%. This decrease is explained by such factors as the improvement of the socio-economic status, the improvement of sanitary and hygienic conditions and the widespread introduction of eradication therapy [5,6].

Results and discussion: *H. pylori* penetrates the gastric mucosa using flagella, where a layer of mucus protects the bacteria from the low pH of the stomach. More than 20% of *H. pylori* strains attach to the surface of gastric epithelial cells. *H. pylori* binds to the gastric epithelium using adhesion factors such as blood group antigen-binding adhesin (BabA), sialic acid-binding adhesin (SabA), extrinsic inflammatory protein A (OipA) and adhesion-associated lipoproteins (AlpA/B)

[4,7]. During *H. pylori* infection, the innate immune response is first activated: pattern recognition receptors (NOD-like and Toll-like receptors) respond to bacterial molecules. Subsequently, an acquired immune response is formed with the participation of dendritic cells, T- and B-lymphocytes. At the same time, the bacterium is able to suppress the STING and pattern recognition receptors (RIG-I) signaling pathways by reducing the activation of interferon regulatory factor 3 (IRF-3), which contributes to chronic inflammation. Activation of immune cells leads to the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines through the nuclear transcription factor (NF- κ B) pathway. Chronic inflammation is accompanied by the formation of active forms of oxygen and nitrogen that damage DNA, RNA and proteins, contributing to mutations and carcinogenesis [8].

It has been investigated that gastric cancer starts with *H. pylori*-induced chronic gastritis and then develops gastric atrophy, intestinal metaplasia, and gastric epithelial dysplasia [9]. The most important factor that determines the transition of chronic gastritis to adenocarcinoma of the stomach are polymorphisms or mutations present in the host's genes. These mutations regulate the intensity of inflammation in gastric tissue, which affects the risk of specific clinical effects and outcomes [10].

H. pylori virulence factors involved in gastric cancer development include cytotoxin-associated gene A (CagA), vacuolating cytotoxin A (VacA), and outer membrane proteins [4,11].

Accumulating evidence indicates that oxidative stress, characterized by elevated levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS), is involved in the development of gastric cancer. Oxidative stress has been demonstrated to be a critical mechanism by which *H. pylori* induces gastric carcinogenesis. This process disrupts the antioxidant defense system and the metabolic balance of gastric epithelial cells, thereby contributing to carcinogenesis. *Helicobacter pylori* induces oxidative stress through excessive formation of ROS and reactive nitrogen species (ROS). This happens both directly (production of superoxide and H₂O₂ in the process of bacterial metabolism, action of virulence factors CagA and VacA), and indirectly - through chronic inflammation with infiltration of neutrophils and macrophages that produce ROS and RFA. *H. pylori* also increases the expression of NADPH oxidase and inducible NO synthase (iNOS), and spermine oxidase in the gastric epithelium additionally generates H₂O₂. In the presence of defects in DNA repair, oxidative stress increases. An excess of ROS causes oxidation of DNA bases, single- and double-strand breaks, and microsatellite instability. If the damage is not repaired, mutations and chromosomal rearrangements occur, contributing to gastric carcinogenesis [5,12].

It is important to note that the clinical manifestations of *H. pylori* infection largely depend on the interaction of three key factors: the virulence of the bacterial strain, the genetic predisposition of the host, and the influence of environmental factors. The latter include the peculiarities of nutrition (high consumption

of salt, smoked and nitrosamine-containing products), smoking, alcohol abuse, lack of antioxidants in the diet, as well as socio-economic living conditions. It has been established that the combination of *H. pylori* infection with adverse exogenous factors significantly increases the risk of progression of precancerous changes in the gastric mucosa.

The role of strains carrying the cagPAI pathogenicity island deserves special attention. The presence of the CagA gene is associated with a more pronounced inflammatory process, activation of MAPK and β -catenin signaling pathways, disruption of cell polarity and intercellular contacts. After transmembrane injection into epithelial cells, the CagA protein is phosphorylated and interacts with a number of cellular proteins, leading to changes in proliferation, apoptosis, and cell differentiation. In turn, VacA is capable of inducing cell vacuolization, mitochondrial dysfunction, and an immunosuppressive effect that contributes to the persistence of the bacterium in the body.

Modern studies also indicate the influence of *H. pylori* on the epigenetic mechanisms of gene regulation. Chronic inflammation can lead to hypermethylation of promoter regions of tumor suppressor genes, changes in miRNA expression, and cell cycle disruption. Such changes form a favorable basis for malignization of gastric epithelial cells even after the eradication of the infection in the late stages of precancerous processes.

In addition, *H. pylori* infection has a systemic effect on the body. A number of studies have demonstrated the relationship between chronic infection and the development of iron deficiency anemia, idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura, vitamin B12 deficiency, as well as a possible role in the pathogenesis of cardiovascular and metabolic disorders. This emphasizes the multisystem nature of the pathogen's influence and the relevance of timely diagnosis.

In view of the carcinogenic potential of *H. pylori*, in 1994 the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) assigned this bacterium to group I human carcinogens. A test-and-treat strategy and timely eradication therapy are considered effective approaches for the primary prevention of gastric cancer, especially in regions with a high prevalence of infection.

Thus, *H. pylori* infection is a multifactorial pathological process, realized through complex mechanisms of interaction between the bacterium and the host's organism. Chronic inflammation, oxidative stress, genetic and epigenetic changes form a sequential cascade of morphological transformations of the gastric mucosa, which in the absence of timely treatment can lead to the development of adenocarcinoma. Further study of the molecular mechanisms of pathogenesis is necessary for the development of new prevention strategies, early diagnosis and personalized therapy.

Conclusion: *H. pylori* infection is the leading etiological factor of chronic gastritis and a key link in the multistage process of gastric carcinogenesis. Persistence of the pathogen supports chronic

inflammation of the gastric mucosa, induces the formation of ROS and RFA, epigenetic disorders and imbalance of proliferation and apoptosis, which contributes to the progression from mucosal atrophy to adenocarcinoma.

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